

Proteomics characterization of RESOLUTE parental cell lines

ID: SP001V-H

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Protocol description

To enable successful SLC function deorphanization we aimed to select minimal number of cell lines covering expression of as many SLCs as possible. Based on publicly available RNA-Seq dataset of 675 cell lines (Klijn C. et al, Nat. Biotechnol. 2015) a set of 6 adherent human cell lines (HCT 116, Huh-7, LS180, MDA-MB-468, SK-MEL-28, 1321N1) have been selective cumulatively covering expression (TPM \geq 1) of about 80 % of all SLCs. These cell lines have been used to generate SLC-knockout and SLC-overexpressing single cell clones. Additionally, Jump-In T-REX HEK293 cells will be used for generating SLC-overexpression cell lines. In order to characterize the expressed proteome of these parental cell lines, we performed extensive proteomic profiling.

Materials

Biological materials:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ HCT 116 (ATCC)▪ Huh-7 (JCRB)▪ LS180 (ECACC)▪ MDA-MB-468 (MD ANDERSON)▪ SK-MEL-28 (ATCC)▪ 1321N1 (ECACC)▪ Jump In™ T-REX™ HEK 293 kit (ThermoFisher, A15008)
Reagents:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium - high glucose (DMEM) Product: D5796-500mL Manufacturer: SIGMA▪ RPMI-1640 Medium Product: R6504 Manufacturer: Sigma▪ McCoy's 5A Medium Product: M9309 Manufacturer: Sigma▪ Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) Product: S1810-5000 Manufacturer: Biowest▪ Penicillin-Streptomycin (10,000 U/mL) Product: 15140-122 Manufacturer: Gibco▪ 1X Dulbeccos PBS without Ca & Mg 1x500mls (Sigma) Product: D8537-500ML

	<p>Manufacturer: Sigma</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Trypsin-EDTA solution Product: T3924 Manufacturer: Sigma▪ NaCl: Product: s7653 Manufacturer: Sigma-Aldrich▪ Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) Product: E6758-500G Manufacturer: Sigma-Aldrich▪ Protease inhibitor cComplete Product: 0505648900 Manufacturer: Roche▪ Phosphatase inhibitor cocktail 2 Product: P5726-5ML Manufacturer: Sigma▪ Phosphatase inhibitor cocktail 3 Product: P0044-5ML Manufacturer: Sigma▪ Benzonase® nuclease Product: 71205-3 Manufacturer: Merck Millipore (Novagen)▪ Alternative NP-40 Product: 492016-100 mL Manufacturer : Merk▪ Sodium lauryl sulfate solution 10% (SDS) Product:71736-500ml Manufacturer: Merk▪ Sodium deoxycholate (DOC) Product: 30970-25G Manufacturer: Sigma▪ DTT (DL-Dithiothreitol), for molecular biology, minimum 99% titration Product: D9779-5G Manufacturer: Sigma-Aldrich▪ Urea
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	<p>Product: U063 Manufacturer: SIGMA-Aldrich</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Iodoacetamide (IAA) Product: I1149-5G Manufacturer: Sigma-Aldrich▪ Triethylammonium Bicarbonate Buffer (TEAB), 1 M, pH 8.5 Product # 17902 Manufacturer: SIGMA-Aldric▪ Water, for HPLC LC-MS Grade Product: 83645.320 Manufacturer: VWR▪ Acetonitrile for HPLC LC-MS Grade Product: 83640.32 Manufacturer: VWR▪ Ethanol absolute Product: 1.00983.1000 Manufacturer: MERCK▪ Trizma® base Primary Standard and Buffer, ≥99.9% (titration), crystalline Product: T1503 Manufacturer: Sigma-Aldrich▪ Empore™ SPE Disks matrix active group C18, diam. 47 mm, pk of 20 Product: 66883-U Manufacturer: Sigma-Aldrich▪ Trypsin/Lys-C Mix, Mass spec Grade Product: V5073 Manufacturer: Promega▪ TFA Uvasol (trifluoroacetic acid) Product: 1.08262.0100 Manufacturer: MERCK▪ Ammonium hydroxide solution 25% in H2O, Suprapur Product # 1.05428.0250 Manufacturer: MERCK▪ Formic acid 98-100%, Suprapur Product # 1.11670.1000 Manufacturer: MERCK
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Equipment:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Covaris type sonicator.▪ Microcon 30, Ultracel YM-30 Product # MRCFOR030 Manufacturer: Merck Millipore▪ Offline HPLC for peptide fractionation.
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Reagents setup:

○ **Stocks:**

- **5M NaCl (250mL):** Dissolve 73.05 g of NaCl in 200mL of H₂O, allow to dissolve with stirring. Then add H₂O until volume is 250 mL. Store at room temperature.
- **0.5M NaCl (100 mL):** Mix 10 mL of 5M NaCl solution and 90 mL of H₂O. Store at room temperature.
- **0.5 M EDTA, pH8 (250 mL):** Add 36.53 g of EDTA to 150 mL of H₂O. Dissolve the EDTA by adjusting the pH to 8 (adding 10N NaOH under continuous stirring). Add H₂O until the total volume reaches 250 mL. Store buffer at room temperature.
- **1M TRIS-HCl, pH 8 (200 mL):** Add 24.23 g of Trizma® base to 100 mL of H₂O. Adjust to pH 7.2 by adding HCl. Then add H₂O until volume is 200 mL. Store at RT.
- **10% w/v Sodium deoxycholate - doc - (100mL):** Dissolve 10 g of doc in 90 mL of H₂O.

○ **RIPA lysis buffer:**

- Composition: 150 Mm NaCl, 5 mM EDTA, 50 mM Tris-HCl, pH=8, 1% NP-40, 0.5% DOC, 0.1% SDS, 1x Proteinase inhibitors, 1x Phosphatase inhibitor cocktail 2, (1x) phosphatase inhibitor cocktail 3, Benzamide.
 - For 100 mL: Mix 3 mL 5M NaCl, 1 mL 0.5 M EDTA pH8, 5 mL 1M Tris-HCl, pH8, 1 mL NP-40, 5 mL 10% w/v DOC, 1 mL 10% SDS and 84 mL of H₂O. Aliquot in 2 mL and freeze at -20 °C. Just before use, thaw the aliquot and complement with Protease inhibitor cComplete (according to manufacturer's instructions, 2 µl of Phosphatase inhibitor cocktail 2, 2 µl of Phosphatase inhibitor cocktail 3 and 3ul of Benzamide).
- ### ○ **100 mM Tris-HCl, pH8:** (200 mL): Add 2.42 g of Trizma® base to 100 mL of H₂O. Adjust to pH 8 by adding HCl. Then add H₂O until volume is 200 mL. Store at 4 °C.
- ### ○ **8M Urea in 100 mM Tris-HCl (UA) solution (10 ml):** Dissolve 4.8 g of Urea in 100 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.5 up to a volume of 10 mL. Always prepare fresh and use within a day.
- ### ○ **500 mM DTT (5 mL):** Dissolve 0.385 g of DTT in 5 mL of H₂O. Aliquot in 200 µL aliquot and store at -20°C
- ### ○ **50 mM Iodoacetamide (IAA) solution (2mL):** Dissolve 0.018 g of IAA in 2 mL of UA solution and vortex vigorously. Prepare fresh before use it and protect from the light.

- **50 mM TEAB buffer** (4 mL): Mix 200 µL of 1M TEAB, pH8.5 with 3.8 mL of H₂O. Always prepare fresh
- **70% v/v EtOH in water** (100 mL): Mix 70 mL of ethanol with 30mL of H₂O . Store at room temperature.
- **50 mM Tris-HCl, pH8:** (200 mL): Add 1.2114 g of Trizma® base to 100 mL of H₂O. Adjust to pH 8 by adding HCl. Then add H₂O until volume is 200 mL. Store at 4 °C.
- **30% TFA in water** (50 mL): Mix 15 mL of TFA with 35 mL of H₂O. Store at 4 °C.
- **1% TFA in water** (50 mL): Mix 166 µl of 30% TFA solution with 49.8 mL of of H₂O. Store at 4 °C.
- **Stage tip solvent:**
 - Composition: 0.4% Formic Acid, 2% TFA.
 - For 100 mL: Mix 97.6 mL H₂O, 2 mL TFA and 400 µl FA. Store at 4 °C.
- **Basic peptide elution solvent:**
 - Composition: 60% Acetonitrile 100 mM TEAB buffer
 - For 100 mL: Mix 60 mL acetonitrile, 100 µl 1 M TEAB and 39.6 mL H₂O. Prepare fresh.
- **Offline HPLC Solvents:**
 - **Stock: 200 mM Ammoniumformate pH 10** (500 mL): Mix 12.628 g of Ammonium hydroxid solution (25% NH₄OH; 35.05 g/mol; 0.91 g/ml), with 450 mL of H₂O. Adjust pH to 10 by adding Formic Acid. Fill up to 500 mL with H₂O. Store at 4°C.
 - **Solvent A: 20 mM ammonium formate in 5% acetonitrile, pH 10** (500 mL): Mix 19.65 g of Acetonitrile, 50 g of 200 mM Ammoniumformate pH 10 buffer stock and 425 mL of H₂O. Store at 4 °C is stable for 1 month.
 - **Solvent B: 20 mM ammonium formate in 90% acetonitrile, pH 10** (500 mL): Mix 353.7 g of Acetonitrile, 50 g of 200 mM Ammoniumformate pH 10 buffer stock. Store at 4 °C is stable for 1 month.

Procedure

A. Cell culture (Day 1-5)

1. Cell culture:
 - Thaw cell line in 6 well plate and incubate at 37 °C for 24-48 h in their specific growth media supplemented with 10% FBS and 1% P/S.

Cell line	Growth media
Huh-7	DMEM; 10 % FCS; 1 % Pen-Strep
SK-MEL-28	DMEM; 10 % FCS; 1 % Pen-Strep
1321N1	DMEM; 10 % FCS; 1 % Pen-Strep
LS180	RPMI; 10 % FCS; 1 % Pen-Strep
MDA-MB-468	RPMI; 10 % FCS; 1 % Pen-Strep
HCT 116	McCoy's 5A; 10 % FCS; 1 % Pen-Strep
Jump-In T-REX HEK293	DMEM; 10 % FCS; 1 % Pen-Strep

- Expand cells on this medium to a 10 cm dish and grow cells at 37 °C until confluency.

2. Cell harvesting and freezing.

- Carefully remove growth media and wash the cells with pre-warm (37°C) PBS twice.
- Add 0.5 mL of pre-warm trypsin and gently swirl it to covert completely the dish surface.
- Incubate for approx. 2-3 min at 37°C.
- Check that cells have been detached under microscope. If less than 90% of cells are detached incubate the cell for another 1 minute.
- Add 9 mL of pre-warm culture medium by gently pipetting up and down and harvest the cells in a 15 mL tube.
- Centrifuge cell at 1000x g for 4-5 min.
- Resuspend cells in 5-6 mL of pre-warm PBS
- pellet cell by centrifugation at 1000x g for 4-5 min.

Note: At this point harvested cells can be flash frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80 °C or immediately lysate.

B. Cell lysis. (Day 6)

- Thaw cell pellet on ice for 20 min.
- Add 500 µL of Ice-cold RIPA lysis buffer per sample and resuspend pellet by pipetting.
- Incubate on ice for 15 min.
- Sonicate cell lysate in a Covaris type sonicator. (200 cycles, 80 s, Freq sweeping, 10% Duty cycle, intensity 5)
- Incubate on ice for 15 min.
- Centrifuge in tabletop centrifuge 14.000xg, 4°C, for 15 min
- Harvest supernatant in a 1.5 mL tube.
- Remove aliquot of lysate (approx. 10 µL) for protein quantification.
- Determine protein concentration of cell lysate.

Note: At this point samples can be stored at -20°C or digested.

C. Digestion of proteins by Filter Aided Sample Preparation (FASP) (Day 7)

1. Protein reduction:

- Thaw lysate and transfer 250 µg of total protein to a fresh 1.5 mL tube.
- Add 500 mM DTT to a final concentration of approx.. 80 mM (i.e for a volume of 120 µL of lysate add 24 µL of 500 mM DTT stock)
- Vortex and spin the sample
- Incubate 5 min at 99 °C
- spin samples and Cool to RT.

2. Protein alkylation:

- Prepare 50 mM IAA solution.
- Prepare fresh 8M urea in 100 mM Tris-HCl solution (UA solution) and add 200 μ L per 50 μ L of denatured sample.
- Assemble the Microcon 30, Ultracel YM-30 filter units and the collection tube and wash the filter unit with 200 μ L of UA solution and centrifuge at $14,000 \times g = rcf$, at 20°C for 15 min.
- Load sample onto filter unit and centrifuge at $14,000 \times g$, at 20°C for 15 min
Note: load max. 250 μ L of sample. If sample volume is bigger, it needs to be loaded in multiple loading steps.
- Discard flow-through.
- Add 200 μ L of UA solution to the filter unit and centrifuge at $14,000 \times g$ at 20°C for 15 min. Discard the flow-through.
- Add 100 μ L IAA solution and mix on a shaker for 1 min
- Incubate 30 min in dark.

3. Protein washing:

- Centrifuge filter units at $14,000 \times g$ at 20°C for 10 min.
- Add 100 μ L of UA solution to the filter unit and centrifuge at $14,000 \times g$ at 20°C for 15 min. Repeat this step to more times.
- Add 100 μ L 50 mM TEAB and centrifuge at $14,000 \times g$ at 20°C for 10 min. Repeat this step to more times.

4. Protein digestion:

- Transfer the filter units to new collection tubes. Add 20 μ L 50mM TEAB in the new collection tube to avoid the filters drying out during digestion
- Add 40 μ L 50 mM TEAB, pH 8.5 with trypsin (enzyme to protein ratio 1:100) (i.e for 100 μ g protein: 2.4 μ L (= 1.25 μ g) undiluted trypsin + 37.6 μ L 50 mM TEAB) and mix on a shaker at RT for 1 min
- Seal the top of the tubes with Parafilm to minimise evaporation
- Incubate the units at 37°C overnight.

5. Peptide collection:

Note: from this step onwards do not discard the flowthroughs and merge all flowthroughs from one sample in the same tube.

- Centrifuge the filter units at $14,000 \times g$ at 20°C for 20 min.
- Add 40 μ L 50 mM TEAB and centrifuge the filter units at $14,000 \times g$ at 20°C for 10 min
- Add 50 μ L 0.5 M NaCl to the filter unit and centrifuge the filter units at $14,000 \times g$ at 20°C for 20 min.

Note: Due to possible evaporation, samples may have different volumes after digestion. Bring each sample up to the same sample volume with water to make further processing steps easier.

- Store digested samples at -20 °C

D. Stage tip C-18 Solid phase extraction (SPE) of digested peptides (Day 8)

1. Acidify sample:
 - Thaw digested samples.
 - Vortex thoroughly and spin down by short centrifugation.
 - Add 5 μ L 30% TFA. Mix thoroughly and check the acidified samples with pH paper strip using 0.2 μ L of sample. pH needs to be around 3. Continue adding 30% TFA if necessary, until reach the right pH.
 - Spin down samples with a short centrifugation.
 - Store samples at 4°C
2. Stage tip assembly: (Original Reference: Juri Rappsilber et al, 2003)
 - Place Empore disk flat on a clean hard surface and press a gauge bunt ended syringe needle into the Empore disk to core out a piece of the filter material.
 - Press a second core into the syringe needle for extra loading capacity.
 - Place the needle into a 200 μ L pipette tip and push the cored disk pieces into the pipette tip with PEEK or fused silica tubing. Gently pack the material into the end of the pipette tip; a gap of several millimetres should be visible between the disk and the end of the tip.
 - Place Stage tips into 2 mL tubes. Use an adaptor to hold the stage tip. The end of the pipette tip should be about 1 cm from the bottom of the tube.
3. Activate and equilibrate C-18 material:
 - Activate C-18 material by adding 100 μ L of 100% acetonitrile and centrifuge at 1000-1600 rpm, RT, 1 - 2 min. Discard flow through. In case liquid don't flow through completely after centrifugation use a small syringe tool to push the liquid manually. Repeat this step 3 times.
 - Equilibrate C-18 material by adding 60 μ L of stage tip buffer and centrifuge at 1000 - 1600 rpm 1 - 2 min. Discard flow through. Discard flow through. In case liquid don't flow through completely after centrifugation use a small syringe tool to push the liquid manually. Repeat this step 2 times.
4. Load sample in stage tips:
 - Load acidified sample in stage tip, centrifuge at 1000 - 1500 rpm., RT, for 1 - 3 min. In case liquid don't flow through completely after centrifugation use a small syringe tool to push the liquid manually.
 - Collect the flow through, load again the column and repeat the previous step.
 - Transfer flow-through into empty brown glass vial. For later QC.
5. Wash:
 - Wash sample loaded onto SPE column with 100 μ L 0.1% TFA and centrifuge at 1000 - 1500 rpm, RT, for 1 - 3 min. In case liquid don't flow through completely after centrifugation use a small syringe tool to push the liquid manually.
 - Discard flow through
6. Peptide Elution:
 - Elute with 2 \times 50 μ L basic elution buffer in a 1.5 mL low binding tube.
 - Evaporate solvent in a vacuum centrifuge at 45 °C until 2 μ L remain. Check regularly and ensure that samples are not dried to completeness! **Note:** Peptides can be store dry at -20 °C until MS fractionation.

E. Peptide fractionation (Day 9).

1. Peptide reconstitution under basic pH conditions.
 - Add 20 μL of 1M TEAB, mix gently and evaporate solvent in a vacuum centrifuge at 45°C until 2 μL remain.
 - Repeat previous step one more time. **Note:** If bubbles are released, add another 20 μL 1M TEAB and repeat the process until no further bubbles are observed.
 - Reconstitute sample in 20 μL of offline solvent A.
 - Test pH on sliced pH strip with 0.5 μL to verify basic pH (8-9 pH).

2. Peptide fractionation:

- Fractionate sample into 96 fractions.
For resolute parental cell lines, a Gemini-NX C18 column (Phenomenex, Inc.) on an Agilent 1200 series HPLC (1st dimension). HPLC solvents consisted of 20 mM ammonium formate in 5% acetonitrile, pH 10 (solvent A) and 20 mM ammonium formate in 90% acetonitrile, pH 10 (solvent B). Peptides were separated at flow rate of 100 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ and eluted from the column with a nonlinear gradient ranging from 0 to 100% solvent B.

Note: Fractions were collected in a 96 well plate. Each well containing 5 μL of 5% FA.

- After offline peptide fractionation: Pool the 96 fractions to 36 vials according to this schedule:

For vial 1: pool wells A1 + A2
For vial 36: pool well
H11+H12
Then each well starting from
A3 to individual vials until vial
35 is reached, then starting
pooling again from vial A4
and so on.

- Evaporate solvent in a vacuum centrifuge at 45 °C until 2 μL remain. Check regularly and ensure that samples are not dried to completeness! **Note:** Peptides can be stored dry at -20 °C until MS analysis

3. Peptide Reconstitution:

- Before MS analysis reconstitute samples in 10 μL of 5% FA. Mix by vortex.
- Samples are now ready for MS analysis. They can be directly injected in a MS device or stored at -20 °C.

Additional notes

- Section: Reagent set up:
 - The volumes shown in this section are indicative. The required volume of each reagent will depend on the number of samples to be prepared.
 - Always use LC-MS grade water for the preparation of all the solvents and buffers.
 - Use only glass pipettes handling TFA and FA.

Data availability

Proteomics profile data of RESOLUTE parental cell lines are accessible on our consortium website re-solute.eu under: <https://re-solute.eu/resources/datasets>

References

- Christiaan Klijn et., al. A comprehensive transcriptional portrait of human cancer cell lines. 2015 Mar;33(3):306-12. doi: 10.1038/nbt.3080. Epub 2014 Dec 8. PMID: 25485619.
- Wisniewski, J.R., Zougman, A., Nagaraj, N. & Mann, M. Universal sample preparation method for proteome analysis. Nat Methods 6, 359-362 (2009).
- Juri Rappsilber, Yasushi Ishihama and Matthias Mann, 2003. **Stop And Go** Extraction **Tips** for Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization, Nanoelectrospray, and LC/MS Sample Pretreatment in Proteomics. Anal. Chem. 75, 663-670.

Please write to contact@re-solute.eu in case of questions or errors.